

ISic4377

Epitaph for Likinis Isauros

Language

Ancient Greek

Type

funerary

Material

limestone

Object

tabula

Editor

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Principal Contributor

Jonathan Prag

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Autopsy

No autopsy

Last Change

2020-11-26 - Simona Stoyanova restructured bibliography

Place of origin (ancient)

Messana

Place of origin (modern)

Messina

Provenance

Excavated in the southern necropolis, re-used in tomb t.18 of Isolato 83, III Comparto, via degli Orti

Coordinates

38.183142, 15.548986

Current Location

Italy, Sicily, Messina, Soprintendenza stores, inventory ME 22797

Physical Description

A square slab of stone, intact, unfinished on the reverse. A six-petalled flower (or star) has been carved out in each corner of the front face, and a similar-sized circular hole in the middle of the top and bottom of the front face; it is likely that these were all inlaid with coloured stone (the lower middle disc is preserved).

Dimensions

Height 30 cm

Width 33 cm

Depth 8.5 cm

Layout

Four lines of simply incised Greek letters engraved between guidelines. The letters become steadily smaller and more compressed

Execution

Engraved

Letter Forms

Simple lunate letters: epsilon has an extended middle bar, upsilon is variable either almost a V or with very curved upper arms

Letter heights:

Lines 1-4: 32 mm

Interlineation

Interlineation line 1 to 2: mm

Text

1. Λικίνις Ἴσαυ
2. ρος ζῶν ὦν
3. ἐποίηι ἐαυτῶ
4. καὶ τοῖς ἰδίοις

Apparatus

Text after Zavettieri 2017

Translation (en)

Likinis Isauros made this while still living for himself and his family

Translation (it)

Licinio Isauro mentre era in vita faceva per se stesso e per i suoi familiari

Commentary**Digital identifiers:****Bibliography**

Zavettieri, G. 2017. Le epigrafi. In Tigano, G.(eds.), *Da Zancle a Messina 2016. Nuovi dati di archeologia urbana*. Palermo. pp. 167-171. At 169 no.1 fig.1

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Cite as:

J. Prag et al. (2020-12-21): ISic4377. <http://sicily.classics.ox.ac.uk>. (Collection: TEI edition). <http://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.4381836>

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